

////////////////////////////////////

INVOLVING END-USERS IN SMART GRID TECHNOLOGY

A COMMUNITY-BASED APPROACH FOR BEHAVIOUR CHANGE

Daphne Geelen / Angèle Reinders / David Keyson
Delft University of Technology, Faculty Industrial Design Engineering
d.v.geelen@tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

Our energy system is changing. From a system with dominantly centralized electricity generation it is changing to a system with decentralized energy generation with a variety of local (renewable) energy sources. To manage supply and demand of energy optimally, a 'smart grid' is created in which ICT is employed to manage and control the energy flows up to household level. Households will increasingly be able to play an active role in the energy provision and their behavior can contribute to the balancing of supply and demand. How this will take shape, and what kind of products and services can facilitate behavior that contributes to optimization of the electricity system, has hardly been investigated in a smart grid context. In this paper we discuss a number of technologies on the end-user side of smart grids and their effects on energy behavior. We address the potential of community-based approaches for design of interventions and products and services. Finally a research project is presented that investigates the potential of a community-based approach for products and services in a smart grid community.

Keywords: smart grid, home energy management, community-based interventions

INTRODUCTION

The system of energy provision is changing. A transition from a system of dominantly centralized electricity generation to decentralized electricity generation is taking place. This is made possible by advances in renewable energy technologies, which are becoming more widely available, and the development of ICT to improve management and control of electricity networks. According to Clark and Bradshaw (2004) and Rifkin (2004), this is part of

a paradigm change in which renewable on-site power generation, also called micro-generation, takes the place of long distance grid-connected power generation based on fossil fuel.

The term smart grid refers to an electricity distribution network that can monitor the electricity flows and adjust to changing conditions of energy provision and demand by using ICT. Smart grids have a big potential for CO₂ emission reduction and less dependency of fossil fuels, because they can accommodate renewable energy sources that do not have a constant output (e.g. the available wind energy is dependent on the amount of wind). Furthermore large investments in infrastructure can be avoided, since the energy system can be more efficient, due to better balancing between supply and demand (peak shaving and peak shifting) and lower transport losses in the network.

The concept of smart grids has conflicting goals and requirements. On the one hand, the goal of the energy sector is to increase the reliability of the electricity provision through better control and management of the electricity flows. On the other hand intermittent renewable energy sources are introduced and end-users are expected to play a more active role in the energy provision. These are elements that are not easy to control.

The shift to decentralized energy generation allows consumers to play an active role in energy provision. Apart from being a 'normal consumer' who buys energy from a conventional energy provider, consumers can actively choose from a wide range of competing energy providers. They can also choose to become a producer of energy and as such participate in the energy market. One may expect consumers to become more energy aware and geared towards ways to optimally manage energy consumption given such a shift. In literature, this new role of consumers is

Figure 1. The electricity system is getting smarter. We are currently in the situation depicted in the middle. With the introduction of smart grid technologies, communication and energy flows to and from end-users and renewable energy generation increases. Source: Technology Roadmaps - Smart Grids © OECD/International Energy Agency 2011, figure 1, page 6.

referred to as co-provider (van Vliet, Chappells et al., 2005) or prosumer, see e.g. (Bergman and Eyre, 2011).

Today's smart grid development mainly focuses on the supply-demand balancing and managing process from the point-of-view of the energy sector (see e.g. (European Commission Directorate-General Information Society and Media, 2009; International Energy Agency, 2011)). A smart grid also requires smart energy behavior of the end-users, since it can contribute to the optimization of the system and increase the sustainability and resilience of the system. The need to involve domestic end-users is recognized, mostly referred to as strategies for demand side management (DSM). However, there is still little knowledge about how the implementation of smart grid technology affects end-users in their daily lives, and in what ways products and services can facilitate energy behavior that contributes to the balancing of supply and demand.

The role of industrial design lies in the design of the technical system itself and in shaping the interaction between the technical system and the end-users, possible by providing insight in consumption and production, by enabling energy management. Additionally, design can play an important role in facilitating the adoption of smart grid technologies. In our research we explore what kind of products and services can contribute to the adoption of behavior

that contributes to the balancing of supply and demand.

The following sections of this paper discuss some of the technologies on the end-user side of a smart grid and their relation to changing energy behavior. The importance of community-based approaches to promote demand side management are addressed and finally the extension of an ongoing study in a smart grid project in Hoogkerk, The Netherlands, with partners KEMA and Hanze Hogeschool.

SMART GRID TECHNOLOGIES AT THE END-USER SIDE

The elements where end-users directly come into contact with the energy system are:

- Smart meters

Digital electricity meters that accurately measure consumption and production of electricity and communicate this data to the energy supplier. Currently they are predominantly used for the benefit of the energy supplier. Some meters can however also communicate with devices in the household itself, such as home energy management systems.

- Home energy management systems (HEMS)

These are described by Van Dam, Bakker et al. (2010) as "intermediary devices that can visualize, monitor and/or manage domestic gas and/or electricity consumption. Their main purpose is to give users direct and accessible insight into their

energy consumption." HEMS exist in various types, ranging from energy monitors to systems that enable you to control appliances.

Most of the HEMS that are available in the market focus on energy consumption and are aimed to assist in energy conservation.

- Smart appliances

Smart appliances are appliances, such as washing machines and refrigerators that can be managed based on the availability of energy. They can be switched on remotely (by householders or automatically) or be programmed on the appliance itself. Also installations, such as heat pumps, micro-CHPs or ventilation systems can be considered smart appliances, since they can be controlled remotely.

- Microgenerators on household or community level
Microgeneration technologies allow households to produce their own electricity. Examples are photovoltaic solar panels, solar thermal collectors, micro-CHPs and wind turbines. The availability of this energy can be matched to the energy demand in the household. Similarly, households in a community can have collective energy generation and/or be connected in a local electricity network (microgrid).

- Pricing and contracts.

Currently the energy price in the Netherlands is a flat rate or is differentiated for day and night consumption. The introduction of smart grid technology allows for more accurate measurement of domestic energy consumption and as a result allows for variable pricing schemes. It can be expected that contracts with energy suppliers will show various options, based on differences in pricing.

SMART GRID TECHNOLOGIES AND USER BEHAVIOR

HOME ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

There is a lot of attention at the moment for the development of home energy management systems. Most of these systems are energy monitors; they provide feedback about energy consumption. The products and services focus on individual users or households, occasionally with reference to the performance of other households.

Research about feedback of energy consumption has been done since the 70s. Several reviews conclude that feedback about energy consumption on its own

can stimulate reduction of energy consumption up to 15%, especially direct feedback in combination with some form of indirect feedback (Abrahamse, Steg et al., 2005; Darby, 2006; Fischer, 2008). HEMS also offer the possibility to display information about energy production, dynamic energy prices and costs. Some of these systems can also be used to actively manage energy consumption by switching smart appliances on/off or turning them up/down. It can be expected that these types of HEMS will have additional effects on energy behavior.

In relation to smart grids, energy management systems are expected to be automated. Users of such HEMS can then set conditions and the system can take over part of the active control over appliances in the home. This happens for example in the Power Matching City Pilot (Bliek, van den Noort et al., 2010). However, HEMS with these possibilities are only recently being developed. As a result there is hardly any information about the effects on energy behavior of these kinds of HEMS.

The development of smart meters, sensors and mobile internet based applications, the increased use of social media offers interesting possibilities for home energy management.

Energy Wiz is a mobile application built to investigate how to design energy-related comparative feedback in such a way that it addresses users with different motivations. The application uses five types of comparative feedback, ranging from comparison with one's own (historical) behavior to comparison and competition with friends on Facebook (Petkov, Köbler et al., 2011).

Energy Life is an application that provides feedback through an ambient display and a mobile display (mobile phone). The feedback is combined with tips and quizzes to increase learning of the user. Furthermore it is set up as a game with several levels that one can reach by reading the tips and saving energy. Results about energy behavior are not available yet (Björkskog, Jacucci et al., 2010).

Whereas the focus of Energy Life and Energy Wiz are on home energy management, other applications focus on games and competitions between (teams of) players. Energy Agent is a mobile phone game for teenagers that fulfill weekly missions and compete in

teams against each other. Savings up to 50% per mission were reached (Gustafsson, Katzeff et al., 2009).

Energy Battle is a game for families in which saving in the real world provides credits for use in an online game. A pilot of the Energy Battle with student households resulted in savings of 24% on average with a maximum of 45% over a four week period (Geelen, Brezet et al., 2010).

These amounts of savings do not stay as low after the games end. The participants did gain more insight in energy use in the house and there are indications that changes in habits have occurred.

PRICING AND BILLING

The way the electricity costs are accounted for consumers has different effects on their energy consumption. Faruqui et al. (2010) studied a number of pilots with in home displays in combination with prepaid energy programs and time-varying rates. The study indicates that the amount of saving was about twice when consumers used the combination of an in home display and prepaid electricity compared to only an in home display. For time-varying rates, users tend to shift the use of appliances to lower priced times. Combined with in home display providing feedback, this effect of load shifting was reinforced. Owen and Ward (2010) examined some of the main issues for introducing varying tariffs for households aimed at reduction of consumption and load shifting. They concluded that households respond to varying tariffs and that it seems to be possible for most consumers to lower their energy bills. They also warn that some form customer protection is desirable, especially for low-income households that do not always have the ability to change their consumption patterns.

MICROGENERATION

Microgeneration technologies allow consumers to become producers of energy. They are not active means to stimulate energy saving behavior, but do tend to have effect on energy consumption behavior. Various studies show different behaviors and behavior changes after installation. Both energy saving and increases in energy consumption were found. "Possible behavior after installation may range from misuse, disappointment/ disillusionment

and rebound effects, through fit-and-forget (no change), to increased energy awareness, indirect benefits and double dividends" (Bergman and Eyre, 2011). Nevertheless it is argued that the installation of microgenerators results in increased understanding of energy, particularly in 'less green' households (Dobbyn and Thomas, 2005; Bergman and Eyre, 2011).

COMMUNITY BASED APPROACHES TO DEMAND SIDE MANAGEMENT

Many programs are being set up to stimulate the uptake of certain technologies or behavior to contribute to management of supply and demand in the energy system. The energy sector refers to these programs as demand side management (DSM) programs. Most programs that were launched until recently, focused on individual behavior. Heiskanen, Johnson et al. argue that many behavior change programs do not address the socially grounded nature of human behavior. They elaborate barriers to behavior change that call for solutions on the community, rather than the individual level and investigate how a number of low-carbon communities can achieve lasting behavior change. A community based approach is considered to be a solution for four persistent problems in energy demand-side management: social dilemmas, social conventions, socio-technical infrastructures and the helplessness of individuals when faced with the enormity of the climate challenge (Heiskanen, Johnson et al., 2010). This notion is strengthened by a seminal work about changing human behavior to prevent environmental problems (Gardner and Stern, 1996). It describes four solution strategies for behavior change: 1) education and information, 2) changing moral beliefs, 3) changing the incentives for a certain behavior and 4) community resource management. The authors found that energy conservation programs are more successful when they incorporate elements of a community approach in addition to incentives and education. A successful intervention thus consists of a combination of strategies.

A complementary perspective on the influence of social context in behavior change is social innovation. Jégou and Manzini (2008) describe it as follows: "The term social innovation refers to

changes in the way individuals or communities act to solve a problem or to generate new opportunities. These innovations are driven more by changes in behavior than by changes in technology or the market and they typically emerge from bottom-up rather than top-down processes." Creative communities, as they call these groups of people, come up with ways to fulfill the needs in their daily life by organizing themselves differently. For instance, the lack of safe roads and proper public transport lead to a 'walking bus'. Parents take turn in walking a group of children to school. The role of design in these initiatives is to facilitate adoption of the solutions by a broader public. In order to establish a sustainable society, the authors argue that designers should rather than translate new technology to end-users, learn from end-users for new directions of technology development. This approach is similar to the recommendation of Gardner and Stern of involving the community in the development of interventions.

To conclude this section, demand side management, or motivating people to adjust their energy behavior, can be done by a combination of technology and social/behavioral aspects. Feedback, information about prices, energy saving options and micro-generation can already result in increased awareness and changed behavior of end-users.

The challenge is to use it in a way that is attractive and meaningful to end-users. Community based approaches, using social learning and participatory methods, can leverage the performance on an individual level. In a smart grid context in which the balancing of supply and demand is highly dependent on the balance in local networks, there is an almost direct relationship between members of a community. In the design field there is increasing attention on how products and services can be designed to facilitate sustainable behavior. Research in this area aims at formulating general design strategies as well as design strategies or guidelines for specific fields of behavior. We expect that a community-based approach in a smart grid community can work very well and that product and service design should take advantage of this.

EXPLORATION OF SOCIAL INTERACTION IN A SMART GRID COMMUNITY

In Hoogkerk in The Netherlands, a smart grid pilot is running since the end of 2009. The pilot involves a number of households that use specific smart grid technology (Bliek, van den Noort et al., 2010). Up to now the research related to the pilot has mainly focused on the technical functioning of the system. There is however a need to also gain insight in the customer side for further development of products and services related to smart grids.

A research is being set up that investigates the effects of the smart grid technology on the households and more specifically on how the community of households can be supported in their behavior to contribute to optimization of the local energy network. The pilot provides a very interesting case, since it provides the opportunity to look into energy related behavior in a community of end-users in a smart grid.

The questions that are addressed in the study are: How does the social interaction affect energy consumption behavior (level and pattern of consumption) of the participants in the smart grid pilot? And what lessons can be learned for product development in this area based on the experiences of the participants?

Since the participants in the pilot form a community, although not yet actively, the social interaction between the community members can be used to leverage understanding and facilitate energy efficient behavior. On the one hand exchange of information facilitates learning among the community members. On the other hand, involving the community in setting up the intervention using the social interaction can improve their motivation to participate. In order to set up a successful intervention, it is important that we gain insight in, and work with, the needs and goals of the households in relation to energy behavior. The goals on individual household level as well as common goals formulated by the community should be addressed in the intervention.

The intervention started in June 2011 and consists of meetings with the participants. These will be used to gain insight in the goals and needs of the community, to create time for social interaction among the

participants, to improve their understanding of the smart grid technology, and to discuss and evaluate experiences and goals of the participants. One of the tools we use to improve understanding and trigger communication is a serious game about balancing supply and demand in a group of households. Next to the meetings, an online platform is created to facilitate communication among the participants in several ways. This platform complements a platform with information on the level of the individual household. What exactly will be on the platform is decided in cooperation with the participants. Elements under consideration are

- Information about the consumption and production of individual households in relation to the totals of the community and the balance in the smart grid.
- Sharing information such as tips for energy saving and load shifting, based on specific questions of the participants.
- Challenges amongst certain participants or the whole community.
- Community improvement activities. For instance initiatives for collective investments.
- Announcement and organization of meetings, such as informal drinks.

CONCLUSION

This paper addressed the role of design in the development of smart grid technology and how products and service design can play a role to facilitate smart energy behavior of end-users. For some of the existing technologies it is shown that they can contribute to a more conscious and active energy management of end-users. We argue that in addition to individual approaches that are currently common in demand side management programs as well as in product design aimed at facilitating sustainable behavior, a community-based approach should be explored in smart grid context. We presented a research set-up in a smart grid pilot that explores the potential to use social interaction in a community for product and service development.

REFERENCES

Abrahamse, W., L. Steg, et al. (2005). *A review of intervention studies aimed at household energy conservation*. Journal of Environmental Psychology 25(3): 273-291.

- Bergman, N. and N. Eyre (2011). *What role for microgeneration in a shift to a low carbon domestic energy sector in the UK?* Energy Efficiency: 1-19.
- Björkskog, C., G. Jacucci, et al. (2010). *EnergyLife: Pervasive Energy Awareness for Households*. Ubicomp '10 Copenhagen.
- Bliek, F., A. van den Noort, et al. (2010). *PowerMatching City, a living lab smart grid demonstration*. Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference Europe (ISGT Europe), 2010 IEEE PES: 1-8.
- Clark, W. W. and T. Bradshaw (2004). *Agile Energy Systems: Global Lessons from the California Energy Crisis*. Oxford, UK, Elsevier.
- Darby, S. (2006). *The Effectiveness of Feedback on Energy Consumption. A Review for DEFRA of the Literature on Metering, Billing and Direct Displays*. Oxford, Environmental Change Institute, University of Oxford.
- Dobbyn, J. and G. Thomas (2005). *Seeing the Light: the Impact of Microgeneration on Our Use of Energy*. Sustainable Consumption Roundtable London.
- European Commission Directorate-General Information Society and Media (2009). *ICT for a Low Carbon Economy, Smart Electricity Distribution Networks*. Brussels, European Commission.
- Faruqui, A., S. Sergici, et al. (2010). *The impact of informational feedback on energy consumption-A survey of the experimental evidence*. Energy 35(4): 1598-1608.
- Fischer, C. (2008). *Feedback on household electricity consumption: a tool for saving energy?* Energy Efficiency 1(1): 79-104.
- Gardner, G. T. and P. C. Stern (1996). *Environmental problems and Human Behavior* Boston, MA, Pearson Custom Publishing.
- Geelen, D., H. Brezet, et al. (2010). *Gaming for energy conservation in households* ERSCP-EMSU Conference. R. Wever, J. Quist, A. Tukker et al. Delft, The Netherlands.
- Gustafsson, A., C. Katzeff, et al. (2009). *Evaluation of a pervasive game for domestic energy engagement among teenagers*. Computers in Entertainment Vol. 7(4).
- Heiskanen, E., M. Johnson, et al. (2010). *Low-carbon communities as a context for individual behavioural change*. Energy Policy 38(12): 7586-7595.
- International Energy Agency (2011). *Technology Roadmaps - Smart Grids*, OECD/IEA.
- Jégou, F. and E. Manzini, Eds. (2008). *Collaborative Services - Social innovation and design for sustainability*. Milan, Edizioni POLI.design.
- Owen, G. and J. Ward (2010). *Smart Tariffs and Household Demand Response for Great Britain*. London, Sustainability First.
- Petkov, P., F. Köbler, et al. (2011). *Motivating domestic energy conservation through comparative, community-based feedback in mobile and social media*. 5th International Conference on Communities and Technologies Brisbane.
- Rifkin, J. (2004). *The European Dream : How Europe's future is quietly eclipsing the American Dream*, Tarcher/Penguin.
- Van Dam, S. S., C. A. Bakker, et al. (2010). *Home energy monitors: Impact over the medium-term*. Building Research and Information 38(5): 458-469.
- van Vliet, B., H. Chappells, et al. (2005). *Infrastructures of Consumption: Environmental Innovation In The Utility Industries*. London, Earthscan.